

Phenylpropionic Acids. Part XII.* The Conversion of Phenylpropionic Acids and their Esters into Thiophen Derivatives

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Phenylpropionic acids or their esters condensed with sulphur when refluxed in 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane to give mixtures of 2,4-diaryl-thiophens and 3,4-di-aryl-thiophen-2,5-dicarboxylic acids or their esters, respectively. The percentages of the components depended on whether the free acids or their esters were used. The structures of these compounds were elucidated by spectroscopic methods and/or by comparison with authentic samples.

WHEN methyl phenylpropiolate (1a) was refluxed with sulphur in dry 1, 2, 2-tetrachloroethane it gave a product which was proved by thin layer chromatography to be a mixture which could not be separated by fractional crystallisation or distillation. However, when the product was hydrolysed with ethanolic alkali, it gave a neutral and an acid fraction (predominant). The neutral fraction proved to be 2, 4-diphenylthiophen (4a) from : (i) analytical data,

(ii) its non-identity with 3, 4-diphenylthiophen, by m. p. and mixed m. p.,¹ and (iii) its n. m. r. spectrum in CDCl_3 (Fig. 1) which showed a multiplet at 2.8-2.2 τ , the splitting of the signal for the aromatic protons indicated that the two phenyl groups are located at different positions, with respect to the sulphur atom. Similarly the free protons of the thiophen nucleus show two separate signals, which indicate that they are differently deshielded.

Fig. 1.

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The acid fraction proved to be 3, 4-diphenylthiophen-2, 5-dicarboxylic acid (5a), since its m. p. was not depressed on admixture with an authentic sample prepared by condensing benzil with methyl thiodyglycollate in the presence of sodium methoxide² (see later). Decarboxylation of this acid gave 3, 4-diphenylthiophen (6a), the structure of which was substantiated by its n. m. r. spectrum in CDCl_3 (Fig. 2), which shows a singlet at about 2.7τ . This stands for the aromatic and heteroaromatic protons. The non-splitting of the signal indicates the symmetry of the molecule and the identity of all the aromatic protons in the molecule, i.e. the protons of the two phenyl groups should be magnetically equivalent. This could be only true if the two phenyl groups are symmetrically substituted in the thiophen nucleus. When the above reaction was repeated with phenylpropionic acid (2a) instead of its ester, the same products, i.e. compounds

(4a) and (5a) were obtained, but the former was predominant.

The formation of 2, 4-diphenylthiophen was, most probably, due to the hydrolysis of the ester to phenylpropionic acid, which is decarboxylated to phenylacetylene prior to dimerisation rather than the condensation of phenylpropionic ester. This conclusion is supported by the fact that when phenylacetylene was heated with sulphur in 1, 1, 2, 2-tetrachloroethane, it gave only 2, 4-diphenylthiophen (4a).

Substituted methyl phenylpropionate and their free acids were similarly condensed and the results are shown in Table 1. *o*- and *m*-chlorophenylpropionic

TABLE 1

Parent substance	Products and Yield %	
	3,4-Diarylthiophen-2,5-dicarboxylic acid	2,4-Diarylthiophen
1a	5a (33.6)	4a (4.4)
1b	5b (35.0)	—
1c	5c (30.0)	—
1d	5d (42.0)	4d (12.6)
1e	5e (28.0)	4e (7.0)
1f	5f (31.0)	4f (2.4)
1g	5g (35.6)	4g trace
1h	5h (32.0)	4h trace
2a	5a (4.0)	4a (82.0)
2b	5b (26.0)	—
2c	5c (25.0)	—
2d	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid (15.2)	4d (31.0)
2e	Anisic acid was only obtained (8.2)	4e (16.0)
2f	5f (1.6)	4f (31.0)

acids (2b) and (c), however, gave only 3, 4-diarylthiophen-2, 5-dicarboxylic acids 5(b) and (c), respectively, whereas *p*-chloro- and *p*-methoxyphenylpropionic acids 2(d) and (e) gave only the corresponding 2, 4-diarylthiophen 4(d) and 4(e). The failure of *o*- and *m*-chlorophenylpropionic acids to give 2, 4-diarylthiophens might be due to the fact that the condensation of the acid with sulphur is much faster than its decarboxylation.

Fig. 2.

The structures of 3, 4-di-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-(5d)³, 3, 4-di-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-(5e)⁴, and 3, 4-di-(*p*-tolyl)-(5f)⁴-thiophen-2, 5-dicarboxylic acids were established by their identity with authentic specimens. The structures of the remaining acids (5 b, c, g and h) were inferred from the similarity of their u. v. spectra with those of 5(d) and 5(e). Decarboxylation of these acids was carried out with copper-bronze and quinoline at 210°.

Authentic specimens of 3, 4-diarylthiophen-2, 5-dicarboxylic acids were prepared by condensing benzil and its derivatives with methyl thiodiglycollate in the presence of sodium methoxide,^{2, 3, 6a, b} or potassium *t*-butoxide. The product was almost always a mixture of 3, 4-diarylthiophen-2, 5-dicarboxylic acid and a benzilic acid. Benzils substituted with electron-withdrawing groups gave better yields of the thiophen dicarboxylic acid derivatives than those substituted with electron-releasing groups. This may be due to the fact that electron-releasing groups increase the electron density on the carbonyl carbon atom which retards its attack by the intermediate carbanion, but they increase the rate of benzilic acid rearrangement.⁷ *o*-Chlorobenzil, however, failed to undergo this reaction, and was recovered unchanged, which may be attributed to steric factors.

Interpretation of electronic spectra :

(a) 2, 4- and 3, 4-Diarylthiophens : The electronic spectra of 2, 4-diarylthiophens show two discrete well defined band systems. Their high intensities indicate that they stand for the ¹L_a and ¹L_b bands. The 3, 4-diarylthiophens,⁸ however, absorb at shorter wavelength than the corresponding 2, 4-derivatives,⁴ and the ¹L_b band appears either as a very weak inflexion or is completely obscured by the intense ¹L_a

band (cf Table 2). This may be due to two factors : (i) The interaction between the two aryl groups in the latter compounds, which partly inhibits their coplanarity with the thiophen nucleus,⁸ (ii) conjugation in 2, 4-diarylthiophens is linear, whereas that in 3, 4-diarylthiophens is a cross one. The former is known to absorb at a longer wavelength than the latter.⁹ Auxochromic substituents in the phenyl group caused the expected bathochromic shift.

The ratio between λ_{max} for the ¹L_b band to that for the ¹L_a band is about 1.25 in the case of the 2, 4-diarylthiophens. A similar ratio is known to hold for monosubstituted benzene derivatives.¹⁰ The similarity between the 2-substituted thiophens and the monosubstituted benzenes was supported by the study of Sugimoto, Nishinura and Imoto¹¹ who found that the positions of the ¹L_a band of 2-substituted thiophens and that of monosubstituted benzenes are linearly related ; but no similar relation was found for the 3-substituted analogues.

(b) 3, 4-Diarylthiophen-2, 5-dicarboxylic Acids : The electronic spectra of these compounds bear some similarity to those of the corresponding 3, 4-diarylthiophens, with the ¹L_b band appearing as a discrete well defined band instead of an inflexion. In the diphenyl (5a)- and di-*p*-tolyl (5f) derivatives the long wavelength bands are strongly red shifted (Δλ 25-30 nm), indicating longer conjugation. (cf. Table 3, figs 5 × 6) However, the spectra are more like those of the 2, 4-diarylthiophens with the maxima appearing at a shorter wavelength, probably due to steric factors, which might force one of the aryl groups to be out of plane of the rest of the molecule. In all these compounds the aryl group in position 3 (or 4) and the

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF 2,4- AND 3,4-DIARYL-THIOPHENS IN ETHANOL

Compound	¹ L _a (Band II)		¹ L _b (Band III)		Band III/Band II	Fig.
	λ _{max} /nm	ε	λ _{max} /nm	ε		
4a*	258	15920	318	15730	318/258 = 1.23	3a
4e	265	36680	~300-330	15040-11090	315/265 = 1.18	3e
4f*	260	27030	312	12370	312/260 = 1.2	3f
6a	234	22270	~254 260	12290-11060	257/234 = 1.09	4a
6b	240	34950				4b
6f	234	25500	~252-270	15000-9749	261/234 = 1.1	4f
6h	238	30490	258-270	21235-19180	264/238 = 1.1	4h

* Demersemann et al¹² gave for 2,4-diphenylthiophen λ_{max} 257.5 nm (ε ~ 12,000) and for 2,4-di(*p*-tolyl) thiophen λ_{max} 262.5 nm (ε ~ 11,000).

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF 3,4-DIARYL-THIOPHEN-2,5-DICARBOXYLIC ACIDS IN ETHANOL

Compound	¹ L _a (Band II)		¹ L _b (Band III)		Band III/Band II	Fig.
	λ _{max} /nm	ε	λ _{max} /nm	ε		
5a	242	20,880	285	10,120	285/242 = 1.18	6a
5b	~230-244	20,900-15,680	278	13,060	278/237 = 1.17	5b
5c	242	23,270	284	11,370	284/242 = 1.18	5c
5d	246	25,360	283	10,090	283/246 = 1.15	5d
5e	228	25,830	284	11,200	284/228 = 1.24	6e
5f	230	25,370	293	10,910	293/230 = 1.27	6f
5g	~234-240	21,170-20,750	288	16,610	288/237 = 1.20	6g
	~Shoulder					

Fig. 3.

Fig. 4.

Fig. 5.

Fig. 6.

carboxyl group in position 5 (or 2) appear to be linearly conjugated with the thiophen nucleus. In the *o*-chlorophenyl isomer, however, the short wavelength band is obscured and appears as a very weak inflexion instead of a discrete band. This is attributed to the steric effect of the *o*-chloro-substituent which forces the phenyl group out of the plane of the thiophen nucleus. The ratio of band II/ band I for these dibasic acids is nearly 1.2. However, this relation is more obeyed in the 2,4-diarylthiophens than in these dibasic acids.

The i.r. spectra of these compounds show a strong band at 1470-1480 cm^{-1} , characteristic of γ C=C of the thiophen nucleus, which is intensified by conjugation with the aryl groups.^{1,8}

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected, i.r. and u.v. spectra were determined by a Unicam SP 200 G and Beckman DK spectrophotometers respectively. N. m. r. spectra were kindly run on Varian A60 by Varian AG, Switzerland.

Microanalyses were carried out in the micro-analytical laboratory, Faculty of Science, Cairo University.

Condensation of Methyl Phenylpropiolate and Phenylpropiolic Acid with Sulphur; (i) Methylphenylpropiolate (6.1 g, 1 mol) was refluxed with sulphur (1.0 g, 1.47 atom) in 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane for 6 hr. The solvent was steam distilled and the product was taken in ether, filtered and the ether dried and distilled

off. The residue was refluxed with 10% ethanolic potassium hydroxide (25 ml) for 2.5 hr, and the alcohol was then evaporated completely (under reduced pressure). The residue was treated with water (20 ml) and extracted with ether.

The alkaline layer was acidified, and the precipitated solid was triturated with hot benzene and the insoluble product was crystallised from ethanol to give 3,4-diphenylthiophen-2,5-dicarboxylic acid, (5a) m. p. 341°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen⁹ (Found: C, 67.0; H, 3.6; S, 9.7%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{S}$: C, 66.6; H, 3.7; S, 9.7%); yield, 2.1 g (33.6%). Its infrared spectrum shows two strong bands at 1695 and 1725 cm^{-1} .

Evaporation of the ether left a brown mass which was extracted with cold acetone. The solvent from the combined acetone extracts was evaporated and the residue was distilled *in vacuo* at 190-200°/12 mm. The distillate was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol to give 2,4-diphenylthiophen (4a) m. p. 124-125° (depressed on admixture with authentic 3,4-diphenylthiophen (6a) (Found: C, 81.1; H, 4.9; S, 13.5%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{S}$: C, 81.2; H, 5.1; S, 13.6%); yield, 0.2 g (4.5%). It gave a red colour with isatin and concentrated sulphuric acid.

Substituted methyl phenylpropiolates were similarly treated, and the products and yields are reported in Table 1, whereas the results of analysis are reported in Tables 4 and 5. Confirmations of the structure of the products were also carried out by i. r. spectra.

TABLE 4—3,4-DIARYLTHIOPHEN AND 3,4-DIARYLTHIOPHEN-2,5-DICARBOXYLIC ACIDS

Compound	M.P. °C	Found %				Formula	Required %			
		C	H	S	Cl		C	H	S	Cl
5(b) (A)	334-5	54.5	2.4	8.5	18.1	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{SCl}_2$	54.9	2.5	8.1	18.06
5(c) (E)	313-4	54.4	2.2	7.7	17.0	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{SCl}_2^*$	54.9	2.5	8.1	18.06
5(e) (B-P)	277-8*	62.2	3.9	8.3	—	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_8\text{S}$	62.5	4.1	8.1	—
5(g) (B)	304-5	58.2	3.2	7.7	—	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_8\text{S}$	58.2	2.9	7.7	—
5(h) (A)	250-1	59.9	4.4	7.2	—	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_8\text{S}$	59.4	4.5	7.2	—
6(a) (E)	113-4§	81.3	5.2	13.5	—	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{S}$	81.2	5.1	13.6	—
6(b) (B-P)	180-1	63.3	3.6	10.2	22.5	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{SCl}_2$	62.9	3.3	10.4	23.3
6(c) (E)	105-6	62.5	3.5	10.2	22.5	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{SCl}_2$	62.9	3.6	10.4	23.3
6(e) (E)	117-8	73.4	5.5	10.6	—	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{S}$	72.9	5.4	10.8	—
6(g) (E)	165-6	66.2	3.7	9.7	—	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{S}$	66.6	3.7	9.8	—
6(h) (E)	151-2	67.1	5.5	8.9	—	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{S}$	67.4	5.6	8.9	—

A = Acetic acid; B = Benzene; E = Ethanol; B-P = Benzene-light-petroleum (b.p. 40°-60°)

* Dann and Hauck⁴ gave m.p. 269°-270°

§ Backer and Stevens⁹ gave m.p. 113°-114°.

TABLE 5—2,4-DIARYLTHIOPHEN

Com- pound	M.P. °C	Found %				Formula	C	Calc. for %		Cl
		H	S	Cl	H			S		
4(a) ^{1,2} (E)	124-5	81.1	4.9	13.5	—	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ S	81.2	5.1	13.6	—
4(d) ^{1,2} (E)	139-140	62.5	3.5	10.6	23.1	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ SCl ₂	62.9	3.3	10.4	23.3
4(e) ^{1,2} (B-P)	204-5	72.8	5.3	10.7	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ S	72.9	5.6	10.9	—
4(f) ^{1,2} (E)	144-5	81.2	5.8	12.6	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ S	81.6	6.0	12.1	—

E = Ethanol ; B-P = Benzene-light petroleum (b.p. 40°-60°).

(ii) The dry mixture of phenylpropionic acid (4.3 g ; 1 mol), sulphur (1.4 g. 1.47 atoms) and dry 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane (20 ml), was refluxed for 6 hr. The cold mixture was diluted with ether, and the ethereal-tetrachloroethane solution was extracted with sodium carbonate solution. Acidification of the carbonate solution gave a semi-solid product that was crystallised from benzene-alcohol, then recrystallised from ethanol to give 3,4-diphenylthiophen-2,5-dicarboxylic acid (5a) m. p. 340-341° (0.2 g ; 4%). Evaporation of the mixed solvent under reduced pressure, left a semi-solid which was distilled at 205-210°/2 mm, and the solidified distillate was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol to give 2,4-diphenylthiophen (4a), m. p. 124°-125° (2.9 g ; 82%) (see Tables 4 and 5), identical with the products obtained according to the following procedure.

Condensation of phenylacetylene with sulphur : A mixture of phenylacetylene (2.4g ; 1 mol), sulphur (0.9g ; 1.2 atom) and 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane (10 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr. The tetrachloroethane was steam distilled and the residue was triturated with ether and the solution dried (sodium sulphate). Evaporation of the ether left a brown solid from which the organic material was extracted with cold acetone. The acetone was evaporated and the residue was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol to give 2,4-di-phenylthiophen, m. p. 124-125° (1.2 g ; 43.5%).

Decarboxylation of 3,4-Diarylthiophen-2,5-dicarboxylic Acids : The acid (5) (0.5 g) in quinoline (1 ml) was stirred at 210° with copper-bronze (0.25 g) for 15 min, then treated portionwise with an equal amount of copper-bronze during 1 hr. The reaction mixture was heated for a further hour, and the cold product was

extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed several times with dilute hydrochloric acid, with water, sodium carbonate solution, then again with water and dried (sodium sulphate). The solvent was evaporated and the residue was crystallised from a suitable solvent to give 3,4-diarylthiophen (6). The results are reported in Table 4. They give a green colour with isatin and concentrated sulphuric acid.

References

1. E. BAUMANN and E. FROMM, *Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 890.
2. H. J. BACKER and W. STEVENS, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1940, **59**, 423.
3. C. G. OVERBERGER, H. J. MALLON and R. FINE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4958.
4. O. DANN and G. HAUCK, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1960, **293**, 187 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, **55**, 3553.
5. H. J. BACKER and W. STEVENS, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1940, **59**, 899.
6. (a) O. HINSBERG, *Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 901 ; (b) *Ibid.*, 1912, **45**, 2413.
7. S. SELMAN and J. F. EASTHAM, *Quart. Rev.*, 1960, **14**, 221.
8. L. W. PICKETT, G. F. WALTER and H. FRANCE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 2298.
9. LLOYD N. FERGUSON, "The Modern Structural Theory of Organic Chemistry". Prentice-Hall, Inc., New Jersey, 1964, p. 503.
10. L. DOUB and E. M. VANDENBELT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2714.
11. N. SUGIMOTO, S. NISHINURA and E. IMOTO, *Bull. Univ. Osaka. Prefecture*, SER A. 1959, **8**, 71.
12. P. DEMERSEMAN, NG. PH. BUU-HOI, R. ROYER and A. CHEUTIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2720.
13. T. BACCHETTI, A. ALEMAGNA and B. DANIELI, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, **4**, 3569.